

ICT-Based system for monitoring air pollution in oil and gas industry: case study- South Sudan

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Abstract- The production of oil and gas around the world have been considered as a major source of air pollution. These Oil & Gas industries release pollutants such as Volatile Organic Compounds, greenhouse gases and particulate matter from various parts of their operations. The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified polluted air as the single largest environmental risk, and hence it is necessary to strive for and maintain good air quality. To manage potential health impacts, it is important to implement proper air quality control management system by understanding the correlations between specific pollutant sources and resulting population exposures. The authorities and oil companies are continuing and strongly committing to research and development to find out reasonably practical measures to reduce pollutions. One of the major challenges they are facing is getting the best solution among different technology applications since it is vital to implement the Best Available Techniques in order to measure Air quality. This paper presents effective method of determining the level of pollution in the oil & gas industries with the low power consumption and cost-effective. To do this, we have utilized the comprehensive ICT-based system using principle of WNS with the target air pollutants which include but not limited to particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), methane, Ozone, VOCs and in addition, we have measured the current temperature and humidity as the baseline. The study is to

determine the concentration of those air pollutants and to further assess the air quality level in the oil and gas industry since their levels present is proven to pose high adverse environmental and health implication such as climate change effects, acid rain, agricultural loss, physiological effects, air pollution caused by burning of petroleum chemical products causing the destruction of zinc roof, decay of concrete walls/ foundations and economic loss. It is therefore the aim of this paper to engage the use of WSN technology using sensors, xbees wireless communication module, Arduino uno, raspberry pi, Thingspeak cloud, mobile app.

Keywords: air pollution; particulate matter; Volatile Organic Compounds; ozone; temperature; humidity; WSN technology; sensors; Arduino uno; raspberry pi; ThingSpeak cloud; mobile app.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, climate change effect is the hot topic by which the world is experiencing global warming as an average of temperature as the result of greenhouse effects[1]. Anticipation is being given that greenhouse effect could lead to a rise in average global temperatures between 1.5 - 4.5° C as early as the year 2030 (Global Warming Environmental Fact (2010) Young People's Trust for Environment). There is a believe that the high increase in the earth's atmospheric and oceanic temperature is from oil and gas related activities. These activities by the oil and gas industries have led to various forms of land degradation and environmental pollution ranging from regular oil spillage, gas flaring down to other minute defects, such as deforestation, burning of fossil fuel, grazing, construction activities, industrialization, residential use of coal and wood for cooking among other uses. Industries, Gases such as methane, volatile organic compounds, particulate matter, Ozone, sulfur dioxide, hydrocarbons are emitted through productions, processing, usage, pipelines, flanges, valves, storage tanks, and waste zones according to EPA. Pollutants are said to be released even during non-routine operations like maintenance and shutdown. Therefore, we need to understand scientifically the sources of pollution in these industries and the nature of the pollutants, in order to develop effective control strategies. Knowing the global scenario and trends of release around various petrochemical sites in the world can give us a big picture of the pollutants that are being identified in the ambient air

surrounding these sources, and the way in which they can affect air quality. Though developed countries have succeeded in air quality management, then still there are further rooms for improvement needed. For the case of developing countries, there is high demands of energy increase, that leads industrialization and population growth to call for better air quality management. Nevertheless, many years have been spent with the study of air pollution and air quality impacts, and the degrees concern varies significantly around the world. This has led to the creation of Air Quality Indices (AQI) [2], which are used for analysis of sever air pollution and the level of risks to health which are arising from particulates and gaseous. Air Quality Indices communicate the exact condition of air quality to people, leading to both awareness, and introspection about, necessary changes to regulations and actions. A variety of indices have been used in various regions around the world. For instance, the Pollutant Standards Index (PSI) established by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA), the Common Air Quality Index in European countries, and the Air Quality Health Index in Canada, to name a few[3]. Many countries follow the AQI established by US EPA with an assigned value of 0 to 500[4], [5]. As it has been identified that Oil refineries can play an important role in the emission of pollutants [6], the air emissions generated during oil and gas production, along with emissions from other sources, could be grouped into three categories: (i) air pollutants (ozone, CO, SO₂, PM, and their precursors, including NO_x and VOCs); (ii) Hazardous air pollutants (HAPs, primarily fugitive VOC emissions from oil and gas production); and (iii) Haze precursors (which include ozone, NO_x, SO₂, and particulates). In addition, (iv) greenhouse gases (GHGs, which include CO₂ and CH₄) are generated during oil and gas development (EPA 2008). Nitrogen oxides, sulfur dioxide, volatile organic compounds (VOC), ozone, hazardous air pollutants (HAP), and methane as pollutants of concern related to O & NG activities (Field et al 2014). Though many literatures revealed that Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂), Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), and Ground level Ozone (O₃) are the main causes of air pollution, our primary air pollutants of interest in this paper include but not limited to Methane, Ozone, VOCs, and particulate matter (PM) as mentioned early since the effect of these gases is being confirmed to have the ability to cause harmful environmental hazards such as acid rain, heat stroke, depletion of the ozone layer, attracting and killing of migrating songbirds, agricultural loss, physiological effects, pollution, and destruction of zinc roof, the decay of concrete walls / foundations and economic loss etc.

For our case study South Sudan, it has been a major concerned that environmental crisis keep worsening on daily basis due to oil pollutions in oil rich area of upper Nile region.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW.

Air pollution is contributing to numerous deaths. In the same analysis done by the World Health Organization (WHO), Air pollution is the main environmental health hazard and it was estimated that air pollution contributed to the death of 7 million people in 2012. Of these deaths, 40% related to outdoor pollution were due to ischemic heart disease, 40% from stroke, 11% from Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), 6% from lung cancer, and 3% due to acute lower respiratory infection (in children). Similar effects were linked to indoor air pollution, with 34% of the deaths due to stroke, 26% from ischemic heart disease, 22% from COPD, 12% from acute lower respiratory infection (in children), and 6% from lung cancer. After the above general overview about the causes of air pollution with effects, we have narrowed down our path to United State Environmental Protection Agency confirmation about natural Gas and Petroleum to be the majority pollutants. According to EPA chart in Fig. 1, Methane, Ozone, VOCs have high percentage of 30%.

Fig.1: Chart accredits to EPA

One example in the support to EPA (Alvarez et al., 2018) above chart is the sources of VOCs in air which were analyzed at Wuhan, China [7]–[11]. Air was monitored at an urban site for 20 months spanning from February 2013 to October 2014. LPG was grouped with petrochemical industry as it is a petroleum product, and then it was concluded to be the direct contributor of petroleum products (Petrochemical

Industry and LPG usage). Besides, we have proceeded in looking at their effects of which it has been said briefly by literatures that Ozone can impact visitor health and vegetation health, growth, and vigor; particulate matter can also impact visitor health and cause haze that obscures scenic vistas. Additional atmospheric concerns include nitrogen and sulfur deposition, which can cause acidification and eutrophication of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems; toxics emissions, which can impact both human and ecosystem health; and greenhouse gas emissions, which contribute to climate change. Below, we have broken down their effects with each and every of them separately.

1. Effect of Methane, Ozone, VOCs and PM on Humans, Animals and Environment.

A. Is methane hazardous?

According to EPA, Methane has not been found to have any adverse impact on human health at concentrations generally found in the environment. Exposure to low levels of methane may cause dizziness, headaches or a general feeling of fatigue. In high concentrations methane will displace oxygen, depriving the body of oxygen which may, in turn, pose an asphyxiation hazard.

Symptoms may include agitation, slurred speech, nausea or loss consciousness, vomiting and headaches. However, Methane can cause change of mood, vision problems, memory loss and facial flashing. We tried to find out its limit but we failed to get current occupational exposure limit specified for methane. Although it is noted asphyxiant, the primary hazard presented by methane is its flammability when sufficient quantities accumulate in a mixture with atmospheric oxygen. When methane concentrations are below 50,000 ppm the gas mixture is too “lean” and there is insufficient methane for combustion. Above 150,000 ppm, the gas mixture is too “rich” and insufficient oxygen exists for combustion. When methane is present at concentrations between the 50,000 and 150,000 ppm it has the ability to combust. According to (White et al., 2018), uncaptured methane source contributes to economic losses, explosive risks and climate forcing

B. Ozone.

The Ozone has been confirmed to have effects on humans and Ecosystem when it is above a threshold of 35 ppbv. The effect on humans according to EPA are: make it difficult to breathe deeply and vigorously, cause shortness of breath and pain when taking a deep breath, cause

coughing and sore or scratchy throat, inflame and damage the airways, aggravate lung diseases such as asthma, emphysema and chronic bronchitis, increase the frequency of asthma attacks, and make the lungs more susceptible to infection. On ecosystem, its effect has elaborated also that, in 2000 global wheat production was anticipated to be lower by 8% due to ozone. In the USA, Western Africa, Europe, and the Middle East, wheat losses up to 15% were calculated. On the same notes, the negative impacts on ecosystems include: loss of species diversity (less variety of plants, animals, insects and fish), changes to the specific assortment of plants present in a forest, changes to habitat quality, changes to water and nutrient cycles. According to EPA, ozone can affect sensitive vegetation and ecosystems, including forests, parks, wildlife refuges and wilderness areas. Ozone can especially cause damage during the growing season. When sufficient ozone enters the leaves of a sensitive plants, it can: reduce photosynthesis, slow the plant's growth, increase sensitive plants' risk of (disease, damage from insects, effects of other pollutants, harm from severe weather).

C. Volatile Organic Compound (VOCs).

According to literatures, VOCs had been said to have short-long term effects on human healthy. Common health short-term problems reported from newly constructed buildings are headaches, sickness, atopic dermatitis, dizziness, sleepiness, irritation in skin and eyes, sick building syndrome, etc, mucous layer of nose and irritation of eyes, confusion, nausea, diarrhea, and vomiting, skin irritants. These compounds are known for the skin sensitizers which mean that skin allergic effect on human and animals also. The long-term health effect of these pollutants may be life-threatening diseases like nasal tumors, leukemia, asthma, nasopharyngeal cancer, and reduced pulmonary function, asthma, lung cancer. Reduced immune system, damaging of kidney and liver such as jaundice, severe respiratory problems, and irregularities in functioning of lung, skin problem like redness and inflammation, impact on our blood system (breaking of red blood cells), mutation, generation of tumors and cancer, and decreased rate of development in body are the grievous impacts [12]. Some other intense diseases from the exposure of these compounds are gastrointestinal and bladder cancer or even sometimes, it may cause damage to the central nervous system, kidneys and liver.

D. Particulate Matter (PM).

Particulate matter (PM) is of increasing concern in recent years as studies have shown links with a variety of health impacts such as respiratory and cardiovascular morbidity, and even lung cancer [13]–[16]. Table 1 shows the various problems caused by PM.

Diseases	Causes/remarks
Asthma	Asthma symptoms can be worsened by increase in PM level in a city [12]
Lung cancer/decreased lung functions/lung irritation	Fine particles directly affect the bronchi, which effects health of lungs and results in cancer. It causes lung irritation, leading to increased permeability in lung tissues
Cardiovascular diseases	Fine particulate affects heart and its functions
Premature delivery and birth defects	PM may pass from mother to the child, resulting in a wide range of birth defects. Lowers birth rate [17], [18]
Premature death	Higher in region with high level of particulate emissions
Vascular inflammation	This is a result of plaque in arteries
Atherosclerosis	Arteries become hard, reduce elasticity, plaque building up in arteries. This leads to the heart problems
Inflammation of lung tissues	Releases chemicals, which directly attack heart and reduce its functions.
Blood chemistry changes	Releases in clots that may lead to heart attack [19]–[22]
Sensitivity to viral and bacterial	This leads to pneumonia in vulnerable person [23]
Other diseases	Increased in blood Pressure BP, increased in stresses, autonomic imbalance and arrhythmias, prothrombotic and coagulant changes [19]–[22]

Table 1 Various health effects caused by particulates matter to human and Animals.

Inhalation of fine particulates that are fallouts from acid precursor gases have been linked to illness and premature death from heart and lung disorders such as asthma and bronchitis. There was ample epidemiological evidence that particulate matter (PM) negatively impact on human health [24]. As the scope is targeting East Africa Region, there are cases of air pollution which have been reported in some oil-rich countries in East Africa and we use South Sudan as one of the case studies examples.

2. Case study: South Sudan.

According to current live situation in South Sudan, the environmental pollution has become a major problem due to the extractions of Oils and they communities have raised their health concerns. This includes birth defects, miscarriages etc. Before we had proceeded, we have first checked back just a little information about what have been reported in media outlets by different journalists who did different interviews with local communities affected by environmental pollutions. According to CNN Journalist-David Mckezenie in December, 8, 2009 at Unity State Oil field area, he has reported that, the Organization called COURTESY SIGN OF HOPE carried out 50 samples of water scientific testing and results came out that, there is high concentration of chemicals which found their ways from oil sewages into drinking waters. The level of air pollution was visually seen from below photo.

Fig. 2: Photo from David Mckezenie's report.

This evident was being continuously reported by SIGN of HOPE that the current negative impacts on humans, animals and environment have a link with oil production activity based on laboratory tests in Block 5A[25]–[27]. This report says about 30 shallow drinking water wells have been contaminated beyond allowable limits set by US EPA and WHO.

In April 22, 2015, another local journalist with the reported on the nature of pollution in the Pariang area. According to local interviewee with the names withheld for security and private sensitivity, he said communities are not safe for 80% and every year, the communities lost about 65% of animals which are dying due to environmental pollutions caused by Oil extraction in Pariang area as example pictures are seen below.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: (a) & (b) are sample photos of dead animals due to air pollution in Pariang.

He added that, the oil can evaporate up to 65km and it affects the lives of human beings and other living animals up to that far distance. The empirical evidence in the literature reaffirmed. For example, in similar contexts, proximity to oil facilities is associated with high risk of cancer (William et al., 2020). Another example, one of the studies in Texas, United States says those living within 0 to 10 miles from the oil refineries were found to have the greatest risks of cancer. This is because direct release of petroleum pollutants affects humans residing near oil facilities through smelling of polluted air, drinking of contaminated water, bathing using contaminated water or eating whatever they grow in contaminated soil (Robert, 1993). A study published in the Journal Cancer also revealed residents living near benzene emitting sites had a high rate of a form of cancer called on-Hodgkin lymphoma[28].

Another study published in Journal Environmental Pollution also links high rates of cancer to living near chemical facilities [29]. As proven in similar petroleum contaminated environments in other countries, more than 10 ug/dL of lead (Pb) in the blood during pregnancy can cause fetal growth retardation, low IQ and low attention, stillbirth, miscarriage, and neonatal death, among other maladies [30], [31]. High lead (Pb) can also cause hypertension and reduce neuro behavioral development (Bellinger, 2005). Men with Pb levels of between 25 ug/dL and 40 ug/dL in their blood have high risk of infertility and other associated reproductive issues (Bellinger, 2005).

A study in 2014 in regard to pollution happen in South Sudan showed that 88.5 percent of the women in the oil producing areas had delivered babies with birth defects [32]. Another report[33] says over 80% of the South Sudanese women living in the affected areas have given birth with children's that have missed limbs, blinds, and deform images(NBS, 2014). The scientific studies shows that the pollution from the oil industries are causing health difficulties including rising numbers of the females infertilities, miss carriages, birth defects, and eyes and skins irritations [33].

According to the latest report by Eye Radio in South Sudan on 23rd, April, 2021 gave the heading that over 200 children are born with deformities caused by environmental pollutions in oil fields according to **Dr. Bior Kuer Bior, the founder of Nile Initiative for health and Environment/Joakino Francis**. A research firm, Nile Initiative for Health and Environment, says it recorded over 218 cases of birth defects over the last three years. These are results gathered from all the oil fields in Unity, Upper Nile states and Ruweng Administrative Area-South Sudan. "We looked through the birth registry and counted the incidents in which women came in and gave birth to deformed babies, so the number that we have recorded came from all the oilfields but the majority of it came from Pariang, part of the number came from many reports that have come to us from many media outlets and also our own assessment at Pariang Teaching Hospital." Said by Dr. Bior Kuer Bior, the founder. This non-profit organization released the report in Juba and Dr. Bior added to Eye Radio that, the number could be more because some cases have not been registered by the hospitals. "The records we have are not really that compressive, so it is possible that other incidents that have gone unrecorded may also still be there," he stated.

The organization also reported widespread environmental pollution with animals and people affected. Both local and international campaign groups say women are giving birth to deformed babies and stillbirths, claims the local people have confirmed. In addition, there were the latest reported in the month of May, 2021 concerning birth defects in both humans and animals by one of the locals in Unity State. This local report is being supported by numerous writers that

produced water, oil spill, and hazardous wastes, among other hazards, are suspected to be the cause of the infertility, skin diseases, miscarriages, blindness, eye infections, eye pains, fatigue, stomach pains, and appendicitis widely reported in various studies. An incidents of birth defects, premature births, miscarriages, still births, blindness, infertility and reproductive health complications, among others. The Ministry of Health of Ruweng Administrative Area in South Sudan reveals that there has been a rise in the number of premature births. For example, 41 premature births were recorded in 2015, 59 in 2016, and 118 in 2017 [30]. “Our team identified 13 cases of birth defects and one case of stillbirth just at one point without household survey”, said by one of the researchers. Most of the birth defect cases include spinal bifida, facial and head deformities, sexual organ deformities, limb deformities, and growth retardation issues, among others [31]. In Paloch oil field, Oil related diseases such as skin itches, respiratory systems, lungs infection, dryness of all trees species within oil produced area were observed, and infections in nervous system where observed and animal mortality were observed. According to the research questionnaire conducted there concerning the types of effect, on the animals, 68.75% answer that there is increase in mortality rate of the animals and 15% of respondents said that the effect is stomach swelling and 8.75% said that effect is eye effect while 6.25% answer that the effect is leg swelling [34]. A negative ecological impact of oil production in Palogue is the emission of oil gases which amounted 40000 M3 /day including H₂ S, CO₂ , CO, C (fieldwork, 2010). Records by Palogue Clinic depicted that respiratory diseases made up 17.44% of total of diseases during 2008 [1].

Based on these problems, there are proposed solutions like bioremediation, phytoremediation, mechanic and chemical etc for reducing the adverse of air pollutions but our focal point is at measurable technologies for scientific prevalent evident to know exactly the level of pollutions which has raised the health concerns. Since we are trying at our ICT field capacity level to establish a quantitative scientific measurements which can be used to understand the extent degree of air pollution in the oil and gas industries, then we shall first look at the related solutions so that we come up with adjustable solution that can suit the current phenomena.

Several documentations have been made in regard to oil and gas industry air pollutions. These documentations include air quality impacts of oil and gas emission from production, processing, refining and use (Air Quality Impacts of Oil and Gas Emissions from production, processing,

refining, and use), which highlighted the major pollutants and regulatory framework. This paper did not reveal the scientific solution, but also ended up with significant evidence on particulate matter (PM), VOCs, and Ozone being the major air pollution contributors. Another research paper (Air concentrations of volatile compounds near oil and gas production: a community-based exploratory study) explored volatile concentration using evacuated sampling vessel modelling methodology. This paper dives deep on the effect of volatile compounds and the only missing monitoring modality. The Best Available Techniques (BAT) pollutants prevention guidelines were applied at Norwegian Offshore oil and gas industry (Air pollution control in a new oil and gas development using best available techniques S. M. S. M. K. Samarakoon & O. T. Gudmestad Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Stavanger, Norway), the major emission was controlled based on carbon dioxide to enhance emission, energy management and energy efficiency, electric power from shore etc. We went through the paper [34] but at energy consumption level, WiFi was used which is not good for WSN battery-operated power devices. So, our system will use ZigBee for wireless communications since it has low consumption compared to WiFi. Second to it, the data visualization and analytics is at the local and we are using cloud server for our data visualizations. Third, it is based on Clustering Protocol Air Sensor and we aim at using K-mean Clustering Machine Learning algorithm.

III. METHOD

We used three methodologies approach *viz*;

1. Qualitative approach, which based on thorough literature reviews. In this approach, no questionnaire was required or carried, our questions and answers were indirectly found in some literature review papers. Also, we did not bother about questionnaires since we are focusing on scientific empirical evidences.

2. Quantitative approach, which based on measuring values/numbers, and this was done by measuring the concentration of methane, Ozone, VOCs and PM_{2.5} at Nelson Africa Institute of Science and Technology-Arusha, Tanzania and another measurement at Unity Oil field-Unity State South Sudan.

3. Scientific methodology, which is based on Agile approach [35] which includes the following phases:

A. System requirements.

It includes hardware (Desktop computer, Arduino, raspberry Pi 3 B+, sensors, breadboards, xbees communication modules), software (Arduino IDE, Python, visio, XCTU), languages (C, CSS, PHP, HTML), webserver (xampp), and cloud (Thingspeak).

B. System analysis.

We did analysis to see whether the identified tools are adequate or sufficient enough for this project.

C. System development.

Our system development started with system design architectural that is seen from Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Our proposed system

Briefly description about system design, in this design system, we have adopted the Zigbee Mesh Network at the sensor architecture nodes or Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) since it is resilience to deliberate damage of one node. The reason for choosing this algorithm to be the candidate amongst counter network topologies is that, there is a cost-effectiveness and low power consumptions etc. Within the circles, it shown the big picture of k-mean cluster algorithm whereby the end devices are flexible to join any router nearby in case they are far away from coordinator/gateway. The gateway will act as a bridge between sensor nodes and ThingSpeak cloud server and finally, the mobile app user interfaces had been developed to access and visualize data through mobile phone or computer base on the user choices. Furthermore, the system design architectural details is viewed from Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Details of one node example of our proposed system

In this detail architectural, we dissected one node only and the rests of the nodes contain similarities. Methane sensor, VOCs sensor, Ozone sensor, PM2.5 sensor, and DHT11 sensor composed the sensor unit which are connected to universal sensor interface which could be a

wooden or plastic circuit board and connected to Arduino uno. Zigbee module which had been configured to be router or end device will wirelessly communicate to zigbee coordinator connected to raspberry Pi that formed gateway. For power supply, there were some flexibilities in power sources. We used power bank to power sensor node and gateway was powered using main supply power of which both were used for demonstration purposes, for general real deployment, solar power will be preferable.

D. System implementation.

We did system implementation by putting everything deem necessary into actions. We first designed schematic diagram that seen in Fig. 6 on how wiring should be.

Fig. 6: Interfacing the system design sensor node

From this hardware wiring, technical details are observed. Methane sensor was MQ-2, MQ-7 sensor for VOCs, Ozone sensor was MQ-135, PM sensor was GP2Y1010AUOF, and DHT11 was for both humidity and temperature and plastic breadboard was used as universal sensor

interface. Xbee Pro S2C had been fitted onto Xbee shield and onto Arduino Uno which the board unit with ATMEGA328P embedded microcontroller for wireless communications between nodes and gateway. Now the real translation into physical mean started by connecting all the components together. Here, they example of those nodes including coordinators are seen from Fig. 7.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 7: (a), (b), (c) are showing Node 1, 2, 3 respectively and (d) shows raspberry pi as a gateway node.

After the connection done, Arduino IDE was used to code/build the firmware which can handle the communications between sensors and Arduino uno. Xbees pro S2C had been configured as end devices and they will pick data from Arduino uno via xbees shield and send wireless to another xbee pro S2C which had also been configured as coordinator and connected to raspberry pi to form gateway node. Python IDE in Raspbian was used to read the serial data from Raspberry Pi and transmit it to thingspeak cloud server. At this point, the data have to be extracted from Thingspeak using python code insert it into database. At the back end, the mobile app called Aireye in Fig. 8 had been developed for data visualization purposes.

Fig. 8: (a) & (b) Show our mobile app interfaces

In mobile app, for security reasons, the interface is created for sign in condition in order to have credentials. After you create an account, you can be able to login successfully and view data as seen in from result section.

E. Testing and integration.

The testing was done at each and every stage in the whole process, the integration will commence at last after which each module is error-free tested. The first test was Wireless communication, configuration was done as follows: 1. Coordinator; one xbee had been

configured as the base station or coordinator, 2. End devices; the other three xbees had been configured as end devices. Since router is required only when coordinator and end devices are far apart, then we did not bother for router since it is just for the sake of testing the system until when we are going to deploy it. Fig. 9 shows the configuration and their communications in XCTU.

Fig. 9: GUI of XCTU showing the configurations.

We switch to console mode and try to type characters “Hii ggj” in order to test communication between two xbees. The blue characters show they have been transmitted whereas they red characters show they have been received. After that, xbee end devices are amounted onto respective Arduino uno and xbee coordinator remained on XCTU in order to observe the live data which had been sent by end devices and received by coordinator as seen in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Showing the wireless communication at the coordinator

After that, coordinator was removed and connected to raspberry pi, the python code which was written and run in thony IDE in Raspbian picked that data and sent to Thingspeak and results are seen in Fig. 14, 15 & 16 from results section 3.

F. Deployment.

At this point, there is no deployment done yet since the project was based on academia requirement but not on the client request. However, it is ready for deployment.

IV. RESULTS

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 11: Showing graphical visualization at Node 1 in Thingspeak. (a) shows methane graph, (b) shows ozone graph, (c) shows VOCs graph, (d) shows PM2.5 graph, (e) shows temperature, (f) shows humidity graphs.

We further checked values.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 12: (a), (b), (c), (d), (e), & (f) are showing the values at Node 1 in Thingspeak.

We proceed to check Node 2 also and its pictures are seen below.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 13: (a), (b), (c), (d), (e), & (f) are showing the graphs and values at Node 2 in Thingspeak

For the sake of minimise too many pages, we did not put Node 3 here, we just proceed to test Mobile app called Aireye with Fig 14 interfaces.

So, we did it so and we are able to access data through mobile as seen in Fig. 14. The options for generating graphs are also available and that we can see graphs at the right-hand sides.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 15: Showing data with graphs being viewed from our mobile app. (a) & (b) are showing data at Node1, (c) & (d) are showing data at node 2, (e) & (f) are showing data node 3.

1. The System validation.

The live data is being sent from each sensor nodes and displayed on the mobile application and graphical visualization is built at each field in the ThinkSpeak. Here we shall do analysis in a comparison to AQI Standards. This analysis will be done in two ways, by comparing our output in normal environment especial within Nelson Mandela African Institute of Science and Technology (NM-AIST) and latter one will be done at the fields where the high concentration of the targeted gases is expected.

A. Analysis at the normal environment Tables in reference to [36].

Parameters	FMEV		WHO	
	Mean	Remarks	Mean	Remarks
Oxygen	97.65	Moderate	86.84	Moderate
VOC (ppm)	240.80	Very unhealthy	240.80	Very unhealthy
PM _{2.5} (ug/m ³)	56.15	Moderate	43.05	Good
PM ₁₀ (ug/m ³)	28.81	Good	17.29	Good
LEL (%)	107.23	Unhealthy for sensitive group	1.028	Good
Formaldehyde (mg/m ³)	2570.65	Hazardous	34.59	Good

Table.3: Air Quality Index (AQI) for the study area

AQI Category (Range)	PM ₁₀ (24hr)	PM _{2.5} (24hr)	NO ₂ (24hr)	O ₃ (8hr)	CO(8hr)	SO ₂ (24hr)	NH ₃ (24hr)	Pb(24hr)
Good(0-50)	0-50	0-30	0-40	0-50	0-10	0-40	0-200	0-0.5
Satisfactory (51-100)	51-100	31-60	41-80	51-100	1.1-2.0	41-80	201-400	0.5-1.0
Moderately (101-200)	101-250	61-90	81-180	101-168	2.1-10	81-380	401-800	1.1-2.0
Poor (201-300)	251-350	91-120	181-280	169-208	11-17	381-800	801-1200	2.1-3.0
Very poor (301-400)	351-430	121-250	281-400	209-748	18-34	801-1600	1201-1800	3.1-35
Sever (401-500)	430+	250+	400+	748+	34+	1600+	1800+	35+

Table. 4: AQI Category, Pollutants and Health Breakpoint

Table. 5 is from (Md. Hasib Bin Hossain Khan Raihan Ur Rahman Md. Yeasin Arafat M. A. Nayem Jony)

PM_{2.5} µg/m³ (24 hour)	Air Pollution Level	Health Implications	Cautionary Statement for PM_{2.5}
0.0-12.0	Good	Air quality is considered satisfactory, and air pollution poses little or no risk.	None
12.1-35.4	Moderate	Air quality is acceptable; however, for some pollutants there may be a moderate health concern for a very small number of people who are unusually sensitive to air pollution.	Active children and adults, and people with respiratory disease such as asthma should limit prolonged outdoor exertion
35.5-55.4	Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups	Members of sensitive groups may experience health effects. The general public is not likely to be affected.	Active children and adults, and people with respiratory disease such as asthma should limit prolonged outdoor exertion
55.5-150.4	Unhealthy	Everyone may begin to experience health effects; members of sensitive groups may begin to feel more serious health effects.	Active children and adults, and people with respiratory disease such as asthma should limit prolonged outdoor exertion; everyone else, especially children, should limit prolonged outdoor exertion.
150.5-250.4	Very Unhealthy	Health warnings of emergency conditions. The entire population is more likely to be affected.	Active children and adults, and people with respiratory disease such as asthma should limit prolonged outdoor exertion; everyone else, especially children, should limit prolonged outdoor exertion.
250.4-500.4	Hazardous	Health alert; everyone may experience more serious health issues.	Everyone should limit outdoor exertion.

Table. 5: Air Quality Index scale as defined by the US EPA (2012)

From above tables, we did a comparative analysis by using them as the baseline to see whether values exceeded threshold values set by US EPA, FMEV and WHO.

<pre> ===== Node1: Methane: 140ppm Ozone: 142ppm VOCs: 148ppm Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 60.39ug/m3 Temperature: 20.90°C Humidity: 76.00% ===== </pre>	<pre> ----- Node2: Methane: 397ppm Ozone: 396ppm VOCs: 390ppm Read PM2.5 with noFilter : -0.57ug/m3 Temperature: 23.40°C Humidity: 68.00% ===== </pre>	<pre> ===== Node2: Methane: 402ppm Ozone: 400ppm VOCs: 394ppm Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 0.13ug/m3 Temperature: 23.50°C Humidity: 67.00% ===== </pre>
(a)	(b)	(c)

Node3: Methane: 607ppm Ozone: 607ppm VOCs: 701ppm Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 643.37ug/m3 Temperature: 24.90°C Humidity: 68.00%	Node3: Methane: 592ppm Ozone: 585ppm VOCs: 623ppm Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 176.01ug/m3 Temperature: 25.50°C Humidity: 65.00%
--	--

(d) (e)

Table.6: (a) Shows data values at Node 1. (b) Shows data values at Node 2. (c) Shows data values at Node 2 subjected to smoke. (d) Shows data values at Node 3. (e) Shows data values at Node 3.

In the morning hours around 9: 09AM, we printed (a) data directly from Arduino IDE serial monitor and it shows that there was no much concentrations seen. In the morning hours around 10: 34AM, we printed another data (b)for Node 2 and we observed an increment in values for all and decrement for humidity. We further did a little experiment at Node 2 to see whether there will be changes, we tried to burn papers. From (c), we observed the increments in Methane, Ozone, and PM2.5 and temperature a little while humidity continuous gradually decreasing.

Afternoon around 1:57PM, we printed (d) data at Node 3 and we observed tremendous increments. After that, we tried to pollute more by burning papers and brought node 3 nearer to smoke again in order to observe results, we expect an increase in (e) but unfortunately, we saw decreases in values. This took us some minutes to brainstorm why again the measured values are decreasing yet we have added more particles. However, we came to a conclusion that, node3 is the first time we connect the circuit, that means sensors were containing high concentrations of those particles that they came with from manufacturing. When they are brought to the normal environment, then they try to neutralize first through diffusions before measure the actual values.

When check our tables with AQI tables, we ignored (c) values which had been subjected to artificial pollution through burning papers and (d) & (e)which did not give us correct measurement. Thus, we use (a) and (b) for this particular analysis under the normal

circumstances, we found that Ozone, VOCs, and PM2.5 in (a) and (b) have exceeded allowable limits.

B. Analysis at the fields.

On 01-11-2021 marks the beginning of final analysis/validation at unity oil Filed Processing Facility (FPF).

Table.10: (a) shows data values taken inside control room, (b) & (c) show data values taken in plants which is outside control room.

In the **table.10**, the data was extracted from serial monitor in Arduino IDE and (a) data was taken inside the control room at Unity base camp. After that, the sensor node was moved outside the and other two (b) & (c) data were observed. The conclusion was that, PM2.5 exceeded the allowable limit according to table 4 & 5. Ozone (O3) also confirmed to be exceeding limit since it has exceeded moderately rang of 101-168 according to table 4. VOC has exceeded the limit inside control room but decrease significantly outside.

On 9-11-2021, small error was identified from table 10 data of which values for temperature and humidity appeared without explicitly showing the word of temperature and humidity, this triggers another measurement by correcting the codes and change the location from control to another room in order to observe differences in measurements.

(a)

```

=====
Methane: 281ppm
Ozone: 259ppm
VOCs: 504ppm
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 80.71ug/m3
Temperature: 25.20°C
Humidity: 57.00%
=====
Methane: 281ppm
Ozone: 259ppm
VOCs: 504ppm
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 87.72ug/m3
Temperature: 25.20°C
Humidity: 57.00%
=====
 Autoscroll  Show timestamp
    
```

(b)

```

=====
Methane: 102ppm
Ozone: 131ppm
VOCs: 281ppm
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 66.00ug/m3
Temperature: 26.40°C
Humidity: 64.00%
=====
Methane: 102ppm
Ozone: 131ppm
VOCs: 281ppm
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 63.19ug/m3
Temperature: 26.40°C
Humidity: 64.00%
=====
Methane: 102ppm
 Autoscroll  Show timestamp
    
```

(c)

Table.11: (a) shows sensor node in IT room, (b) shows data values taken inside IT room when room was closed.

In table 11, (b) data was taken at around 2:00PM as initial data, after that, the room was closed with the air conditioning working in order to observe whether the air conditioning can have influent by either decreasing or increasing some parameters. After 40 Minutes, (c) data reading was taken and observed that there is decrease from first four parameters accept temperature and humidity that shown increment. So, on safety matter, ozone seems to be normal inside when room was closed. VOCs observed to above limit prescripts by table 3. PM2.5 exceeded limit according to table 3 & 5 but table 4 accepted it to be moderate.

After that, the sensor was moved to outside and another data was observed in table 12.

(a)

```
=====  
Methane: 168ppm  
Ozone: 230ppm  
VOCs: 350ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 101.73ug/m3  
Temperature: 33.70°C  
Humidity: 54.00%  
=====  
Methane: 167ppm  
Ozone: 230ppm  
VOCs: 350ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 117.15ug/m3  
Temperature: 33.70°C  
Humidity: 54.00%  
=====  
Methane: 166ppm  
 Autoscroll  Show timestamp
```

(b)

Table.12: (a) shows sensor node outside IT room, (b) data values taken outside IT room.

In table 12, only ozone and humidity have shown the decrease and the rests of the parameters have shown increments. So, ozone still normal outside while VOCs and PM2.5 maintain their threats continuity. Again, the sensor was moved to nearby the crude oil pond as seen from table 13.


```
=====  
Methane: 236ppm  
Ozone: 359ppm  
VOCs: 523ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 139.57ug/m3  
Temperature: 39.80°C  
Humidity: 42.00%  
=====  
Methane: 235ppm  
Ozone: 361ppm  
VOCs: 522ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 147.98ug/m3  
Temperature: 39.80°C  
Humidity: 42.00%  
=====  
Methane: 188ppm  
 Autoscroll  Show timestamp
```

(a)

(b)

Table.13: (a) shows sensor node at the crude oil pond, (b) shows data values taken at crude oil pond.

In table 13, it was observed that the first five parameters swiftly increased, only humidity decreased. Of course, it is obvious for the pond side to be the dangerous place to stay in for long. As the node was moving away to somewhere in the plants, concentration decreased. Table 14. Shown the data taken in plants.

(a)

```
=====  
Methane: 127ppm  
Ozone: 178ppm  
VOCs: 314ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 103.83ug/m3  
Temperature: 35.30°C  
Humidity: 53.00%  
=====  
Methane: 127ppm  
Ozone: 176ppm  
VOCs: 314ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 103.83ug/m3  
Temperature: 35.30°C  
Humidity: 53.00%  
=====  
 Autoscroll  Show timestamp
```

(b)

Table.14: (a) shows sensor node at field facility, (b) shows data values taken at field facility.

Here in table 14, all the parameters have decreased except humidity. Finally, the job ended at firebase residential where the last process was taken.

(a)

```
=====  
Methane: 103ppm  
Ozone: 135ppm  
VOCs: 256ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 131.16ug/m3  
Temperature: 31.80°C  
Humidity: 65.00%  
=====  
Methane: 103ppm  
Ozone: 134ppm  
VOCs: 256ppm  
Read PM2.5 with noFilter : 71.60ug/m3  
Temperature: 31.80°C  
Humidity: 65.00%  
=====  
 Autoscroll  Show timestamp
```

(b)

Table.15: (a) shows sensor node at firebase compound, (b) show data values taken at firebase compound.

In table 15, we observed that VOCs and particulate matter PM2.5 exceeded the allowable limits according to table. 3. Table 4 shows PM2.5 and O_3 to be in moderated.

V. DISCUSSION

In our system, Zigbee-based wireless Mesh Network which operates in the unlicensed 2.4 GHz, 915 MHz and 868 MHz ISM bands with data rates from 20-250 Kbps [37] was adopted at the sensor nodes architecture or Wireless Sensor Network (WSN). The reason for choosing this algorithm to be the candidate amongst counter network topologies is that, it is a cost-effectiveness and self-organizing low power consumptions. we used Xbee shield to fit Xbee Pro S2C wireless module on Arduino Uno for wireless communications between nodes and gateway.

At sensor unit, we used the following sensors: (a) MQ-2 sensor of which the literatures confirmed to be not detecting only methane which is an example of greenhouse gas which has

been said to be a bacterial transformation of CO₂[38] but also butane, propane and natural gas; (b) MQ-7 sensor for detecting various VOCs (Volatile Organic Compounds) which are hydrocarbons, both aliphatic and aromatic that are generated from the petroleum industry [39]. These Aromatic VOCs are mainly comprised of Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, and Xylene (BTEX)[40]. In addition, another literature added that high concentration of carbon dioxide can lead to VOC. Other major of VOCs are ethene, propene, 1-butene, C₂-C₄ alkanes, hexane, cyclohexane, methylcyclohexane, isopropylbenzene, and styrene [41]; (c) MQ-135 Sensor for detecting Ozone which is a secondary pollutant that is formed from the reaction between VOCs, oxides of nitrogen, and sunlight. This ozone production depends on the amount of VOCs, NO_x, and also the ratio of VOC/NO_x. There is also a correlation which has been mentioned that high concentration of methane can lead to ozone; (d) PM_{2.5}: based on the formation mechanism, particulate matter can be classified into two types namely; primary and secondary particulate matter. Primary particulate matter is directly emitted from the source to the atmosphere, and a major source from the petroleum refining industry is the Fluid Catalytic Cracking Unit (FCC) [42]. Secondary particulate matter is mainly formed in the atmosphere from precursor gases like SO₂, NO_x and VOCs. Secondary aerosol includes particulates formed as secondary organic aerosols (SOA) as a result of the atmospheric and photochemical oxidation of VOCs. These both primary and secondary contributors are potentially toxic, and their association with the atmosphere aerosols can have adverse health impacts [43], [44]. Therefore, we used GP2Y1010AUOF dust smoke particle sensor for detecting PM_{2.5}. The main board is an Arduino Uno with ATMEGA328P embedded micro controller and we used Arduino IDE to code/build the firmware which can handle the communications between sensors and Arduino uno. The gateway will act as a bridge between sensor nodes and ThingSpeak cloud server. At the gateway, we used Raspberry Pi 3 model B+ with Raspbian OS and the reason is that it has its own wifi capabilities. We wrote python code using Thony IDE to read data serially from raspberry pi. In this Project, the ThingSpeak cloud-base is the best choice based on its easiest accessibilities and efficiency of data visualizations and above all, at economical aspect, it is an open source which means we paid nothing. This ThingSpeak cloud service allows data collection, aggregation, data visualization, and analyze pollution data streams and gives the expected results. In ThingSpeak, MATLAB software runs automatically the data analytics based on schedules and events. Data was extracted from Thingspeak and inserted into database which was created using mysql. The

last portion is the user interfaces, the mobile app has been developed to access and visualize data through mobile phone or computer base on the user choices.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on other literature reviewed, we have concluded that Air pollution monitoring needs an eye-open globally due to its harmful effect on the environment and human health. This can be simply well understood without hesitations. Population increase and fast industrialization cause major environmental deprivation like air, water, and land pollution. To do this, the ICT-based system is a solution perfectly matched to fight environmental threats, in our system, our developed ICT-based has captured the required aspects for environmental monitoring, particularly the air pollution monitoring system in oil and gas industry. Hence, the system is best suited to improve environmental pollution in East Africa, particularly South Sudan. Because of its cost effectiveness and easily accessibility, it has fulfilled the intended goal of improving air pollution by revealing the air pollution status to Health Safety Environment (HSE) department or concern body. The process is through collecting environmental parameters from sensor nodes, to transmit to Thingspeak platform via coordinator, and then to be displayed either direct from Thingspeak or from Mobile app via database. However, though we aimed initially that our proposed system needs to maximizes the measurement of air pollution in the Oil and Gas Industry, there are things that we ended up not to cover, these as follows: the data extraction from Thingspeak to database has not been automated, it has to be extracted manually using python codes and we found it very unconvince. This gap needs further development. Based on particulate Matter detection, we detected only PM_{2.5} since we failed to get the sensors which can detect PM₁, PM₁₀. Our failure to measure these two particulate Matter (PM₁ and PM₁₀) left the further measurement of the particulate Matter 1 and 10. According to some other literatures, MQ-131 is most used to detect Ozone but we failed to get this particular sensor and we just used the general air quality MQ-135. Therefore, there is a need at least for this MQ-131 series for the perfect detection of Ozone.

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